

DETECTION OF CANE SUGAR IN MILK AND ITS PRODUCTS

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For the detection of cane sugar in milk and its products, the resorcin-hydrochloric acid (Seliwanoff reagent) test is widely used, a positive reaction being indicated by the production of a red colour. This test is characteristic of a ketose sugar, such as, levulose, but cane sugar is rapidly hydrolysed to glucose and levulose in presence of hot acid and so affords a positive reaction. Cane sugar is commonly employed to raise the sp. gravity and the solids-not-fat of watered milk to make it pass the minimum legal standards. In the preparation of Seliwanoff reagent, Jacobs dissolved 0.05 g. of resorcin in 100 ml. of 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid¹, whereas elsewhere the same author dissolved² 0.05 g. of resorcin in 100 ml. of 1 : 2 hydrochloric acid, *i.e.* one volume of concentrated hydrochloric acid mixed with two volumes of water,³ therefore, the concentration of acid in the latter reagent was less.

It was observed that the time of heating and the concentration of hydrochloric acid³ of the Seliwanoff reagent (the amount of resorcin remaining constant) had a considerable effect on the intensity of the red colour developed. It was further seen that reconstituted milk, prepared from milk powder, and heated milk gave a distinct red colour when subjected to the resorcin test using the Seliwanoff reagent prepared with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, although they did not contain any cane sugar or levulose. There is therefore the risk that milk powder or reconstituted milk may be *misreported* as having contained cane sugar, if this concentration of hydrochloric acid is used for the test. On the other hand, use of 1 : 2 hydrochloric acid instead of 1 : 1 in the Seliwanoff reagent failed to produce a decisively positive result in milk containing small amounts of cane sugar of the order of 0.5% and below. In determining therefore the optimum concentration of hydrochloric acid for the Seliwanoff reagent, an intermediate course was adopted, and experiments were carried out with Seliwanoff reagent prepared with 1 : 1.5 hydrochloric acid, *i.e.*, one volume of conc. hydrochloric acid mixed with 1.5 volumes of water. This was strikingly successful as shown later. With this concentration of acid, reconstituted milk and boiled milk did not give positive results and at the same time as little as 0.25% of cane sugar in milk could be detected.

In regard of the *time* of heating, it was observed that half-a-minute's heating was too short to provide any conclusive result; also, excessive prolonging of the heating time produced erratic results. One minute's heating was found to be reasonable and furnished reproducible results.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments, recorded below, were carried out, varying the concentration of HCl in the Seliwanoff reagent (keeping the amount of resorcin the same) with fresh milk, boiled and reconstituted milks and with milk containing different proportions of added cane sugar.

TABLE I

Reagents.			
Seliwanoff reagent No. I :	Resorcin (0.05 g.)	dissolved in 100 ml. of	1 : 1 HCl
" "	No. II :	" "	" "
" "	No. III :	" "	1 : 2 HCl
" "	" "	" "	1 : 1.5 HCl

The above reagents were prepared by dilution of HCl (*d* 1.18)

The Test.—A little of the sample of milk was curdled by adding HCl and standing, and was filtered. (Usually 25 ml. of milk curdled well with 1 ml. of conc. HCl and this procedure was followed). To 5 ml. of the above three Seliwanoff reagents, in separate test tubes, was added 1 ml. of the clear milk serum; the solutions were mixed and the test tubes were put in boiling water (in a beaker or a suitable vessel) for *exactly one minute*, the time being noted by a stop-watch. The tubes were immediately withdrawn and the colour of the solution was observed after one minute. A red colour indicates a positive result. Observations made are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

	Reagent I. (1 : 1 HCl)	Reagent II. (1 : 2 HCl)	Reagent III (1 : 1.5 HCl)
Fresh, genuine milk	Very slight red colour, almost negligible	No colour	No colour
Fresh milk boiled down to half volume	Distinct red colour	Do	Do
Fresh milk +0.1% added cane sugar	Red colour	Do	Slight red colour
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	Do	Do	Distinct red colour
Do+0.5% of added cane sugar	Do	Do	Red colour
Reconstituted milk prepared from milk powder	Distinct red colour	Do	No colour

The above experiments were carried out with four samples of cow-milk and four of buffalo-milk, these two types being most commonly consumed. Observations in each case were similar. The optimum concentration of hydrochloric acid in the Seliwanoff reagent is therefore 1:1.5, as at this

concentration boiled milk and reconstituted milk do not produce any red colour and as little as 0.25% of cane sugar may be detected with certainty.

Effect of formalin.—For analysis under the Food Adulteration Act, milk samples are usually despatched preserved with a few drops of formalin. It was therefore necessary to carry out the above experiments with milk preserved with formalin. The observations made with formalinised milk are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Interference in case of milk :	Reagent I (1 : 1 HCl).	Reagent II (1 : 2 HCl).	Reagent III (1 : 1.5 HCl).
Genuine milk preserved with formalin (1 drop per oz. milk)	Pink coloured curdy ppt. separates—serum had no colour	Curdy ppt. only	Curdy ppt. only
Do+0.5% added cane sugar	No red colour	No red colour	No red colour
Do+1.0% added cane sugar	Do	Do	Do
<i>Interference in case of sugar syrup :</i>			
1 ml. of 25% cane sugar solution in water+1 drop of formalin	Do	Do	Do
1 ml. of 40% cane sugar solution in water+1 drop of formalin	Do	Do	Do

Table III clearly indicates that presence of even small amounts of formalin, as is usually used in milk preservation, interferes with the test and prevents colour formation even when significant amounts of cane sugar are present. To obviate this difficulty the amount of resorcin in Seliwanoff reagent was increased from 0.05 to 1.0 g. while keeping the concentration of HCl at the optimum level of 1:1.5. The modified Seliwanoff reagent (call this reagent IV) was prepared by dissolving 1.0 g. of resorcin in 100 ml. of 1:1.5 HCl. The reagent IV was then tested with pure cane sugar solution in water with formalin added, and side by side the same experiment was carried out with reagents No. I, II and III for comparison, with the following results.

TABLE III A

	Reagent I.	Reagent II.	Reagent III.	Reagent IV.
1 ml. of 20% cane sugar soln. in water+2 drops of formalin (one sample)	...	...	...	Intensely red colour
1 ml. of 2.0% cane sugar soln. in water+2 drops of formalin (one sample)	No colour	No colour	No colour	Strongly red colour

Next, the reagent IV was employed to detect cane sugar in milk preserved with varying amounts of formalin. The results are summarised in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Samples	Number of samples.	Observation.
Fresh, genuine milk preserved with formalin (1 drop of formalin per oz. of milk)	4	No colour
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	4	Distinct red colour
Do+0.5 " "	4	Red colour
Do+1.0 " "	4	Do
*Fresh milk preserved with excess of formalin (3 drops of formalin per oz. of milk)	3	No colour
Do+ .25% added cane sugar	3	Slight red colour
Do+0.5 " "	3	Distinct red colour
Do+1.0 " "	3	Red colour
*Fresh milk preserved with excess of formalin (5 drops of formalin per oz. of milk)	3	No colour
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	3	Slight red colour
Do+0.5 " "	3	Distinct red colour
Do+1.0 " "	3	Red colour
Reconstituted milk made from milk powder and preserved with formalin (3 drops per oz.)	2	No colour
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	2	Slight red colour
Do+0.5 " "	2	Distinct red colour
Do+1.0 " "	2	Red colour

*In practice use of so much of formalin as three to five drops per oz. is not met with, and usually two to four drops are added to a four-oz. sample.

Having succeeded with formalinised milk containing sugar by the use of the reagent IV, it was necessary to see how this reagent worked with plain milk, *i.e.* not containing any formalin. The resorcin test was therefore carried out on fresh milk without any formalin, boiled milk, reconstituted milk and milk containing different proportions of added cane sugar, using the reagent IV. Observations are summarised in Table V.

TABLE V

Samples	No. of samples.	Observation.
Fresh milk (without formalin)	4	No colour
Do+ boiled down to half volume	4	Do
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	4	Distinct red colour
Do+0.5 " "	4	Red colour
Do+1.0 " "	4	Do
Reconstituted milk made from milk powder (without formalin)	4	No colour
Do+0.25% added cane sugar	4	Distinct red colour
Do+0.5 " "	4	Red colour
Do+1.0 " "	4	Do

The above observations clearly indicate that the reagent IV is ideally suited for the detection of cane sugar in milk, milk powder and reconstituted

milk, whether preserved with formalin or not. In conclusion, the final recommended method for the detection of cane sugar in milk, milk powder and reconstituted milk, is, as follows.

Final modified method for the detection of cane sugar in milk and its products.— Prepare the modified Seliwanoff reagent by dissolving 1.0 g of resorcin, A.R. in 100 ml. of dilute HCl (1:1.5), i.e. 1 volume of conc. hydrochloric acid of sp.gr. 1.18 mixed with 1.5 volumes of distilled water. Curdle an aliquot part of the sample of milk by adding a little hydrochloric acid, keep it standing for about ten minutes and filter (the filtrate should be reasonably clear—usually 1 ml. of conc. hydrochloric acid is required for 25 ml. of milk for satisfactory curdling). To 5 ml. of the modified Seliwanoff reagent in a test tube, add 1 ml. of the milk serum and mix. Place the tube in boiling water in a beaker or a suitable vessel, so that the level of the boiling water is not lower than that of the liquid in the test tube, for *exactly one minute*, the time being noted by a stop-watch. Immediately withdraw the tube from the water bath and observe the colour of the liquid after one minute. A red colour indicates the presence of cane sugar or a ketose sugar like levulose.

This method is in continuous use in this laboratory and is providing conspicuously uniform results.

S U M M A R Y

In the detection of cane sugar in milk and reconstituted milk by the resorcin-Seliwanoff test it was observed that the concentration of HCl in the Seliwanoff reagent and the time of heating had considerable effect on the development of red colour. 1:1 HCl in the Seliwanoff reagent gave a positive result for cane sugar in milk reconstituted from milk powder although it did not contain any cane sugar, and on the other hand 1:2 HCl failed to detect small amounts of cane sugar, 0.5% or below. The optimum concentration of HCl in Seliwanoff reagent was found to be 1:1.5, as with this concentration no red colour was obtained with reconstituted milk and as little as 0.25% of cane sugar could be detected. Also, the optimum time of heating was found to be one minute.

For milk preserved with formalin and containing even appreciable amount of sugar, the Seliwanoff reagent prepared with 0.05 g. of resorcin failed to give positive results. The same observation was also made with concentrated sugar syrups in water preserved with a little formalin. This difficulty was overcome by increasing the amount of resorcin from 0.05 g. to 1.0 g. dissolved in 100 ml. of 1:1.5 hydrochloric acid in the Seliwanoff reagent. By this modified reagent, as little as 0.25% of cane sugar could be detected in milk, whether preserved with formalin or not.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Jacobs, "The Chemical Analysis of Foods and Food Products", 3rd print., 1945, D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 173-4.
2. Jacobs, *ibid.*, p. 250.
3. Woodman, "Food Analysis", 1941, 4th Ed., McGraw-Hill Book Co. Inc., New York and London, 262.